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Relationship between socialisation and individual's conduct in society

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Abstract: Socialization is a complex process that must be known by social workers. The process of socialization is a complex phenomenon that implies multiple socializing agents (family, school, workplace, entourage, neighbors etc) that take place step by step. Primary socialization is encountered during the first years of life, followed by secondary socialization during scholastic education and finally is completed by the continuous socialization for the rest of one's life. Different styles of parenting have been put into relation (authoritarian, permissive, warm, cold), and their respective long term effects. The current paper presents a holistic vision over socialization, a process that give the individual legitimacy in society by embracing adequate social patterns of behaviour. The second part of this paper is regarding deficient socialization and it's relation with deviant behavior.

Keywords: socialization, family, behavior, conduct

General concepts of socialization within the family

Family represents a form of human community made up of at least two individuals united by marriage or descent, linked to each other by biological, economic, moral-emotional, legal relationships, who have certain rights and obligations, carry out a series of activities and fulfill certain functions.

The sociological perspective defines the family as the social group built on the basis of marriage, consanguinity and kinship relationships in which group members share common aspirations and values. The family is a primary group in which relationships are direct, informal and unmediated.

The legal perspective defines the family as the group of people between whom a set of rights and obligations legally regulated by normative acts is established (Bulgaru, 2003). Unrealistic expectations through rigid requirements regarding behaviour, cleanliness, grades at school will have repercussions that will be felt even in adult life. In this respect, psychologist Erikson distinguishes two stages of the child's development that the parent must take into account. The "conflict between initiative and guilt" stage, which lasts until around the age of 5, is characterized by the child's desire to interact with others, an initiative which, if restricted, may become a defining feature of the child's personality and later of the adult's. The "conflict between diligence and inferiority" stage lasts until around the age of 12, when the child starts school. If the demands of the primary school teacher, teachers, parents are in relation to his capabilities, the child will develop diligence and progress. Nevertheless, the problem arises when both the family and the teaching staff have unrealistic expectations of the child that he or she does not meet. In this case, there is a risk of abandoning the assigned tasks (children do not do their homework, they feel inferior, there is a risk of dropping out of school), etc. Thus, children raised in institutions without the presence of parental functions end up being socially maladjusted adults precisely on the basis of these conflicts described by Erikson that have internalized in the individual.

1. Ability to perceive the child realistically - refers to the attitude and behaviour towards the child. This attitude is given by the image we have of the child. Often there are conflict situations between parents and children precisely because of the formation of a wrong global image of the child.
2. Ability to reward and value the child_- the parent must reward the positive behaviour of the child. Many parents do not praise their own children's positive behaviour but instead unequivocally punish the negative. It is a mistake for the parent to focus his attention only on the wrong behaviours of his own child (coord. Neamțu & Muntean, 2003)

Socialisation, main actor of human shaping

Socialisation is essentially a psychosocial process through which values, knowledge and behavioural patterns specific to a group are transmitted and assimilated for social formation and adaptation. Socialisation should be seen as a dynamic interactive process. Through socialisation the biological organism is transformed into a social being that is able to react together with others. Without socialisation, the individual and society could not survive (Bulgaru, 2003) Even in the famous cases of the "wolves" children Amala and Kamala we refer to a certain kind of "socialisation" in the animal world. The two little girls found in the wild had a series of behaviours similar to those of animals, most likely copied by imitating the "parent" in our case, the wolf family (they hunted, walked on all fours, drooled excessively, ate meat not thermally prepared, preferred darkness to the light of day. All these behaviours that are not found in children in the human world show that even in the animal world a "rudimentary socialisation" occurs. Socialisation as a process begins at birth due to the first contacts with the environment and with parents, especially with the mother, and extends throughout life.

Primary socialisation and personality shaping

Although all levels of the socialisation process are important, the primary socialisation stage influences the development of the child most spectacularly. In the first years of life, parents are agents of socialisation. From the youngest ages, two types of influence act on the child : certain are spontaneous-unintentional, while others are intentional and aim at education per se. Sometimes it is important to focus our attention on the unintended influences parents have upon children. The latter may have dramatic consequences. Thus, the inconsistency between the parent's requirements and the model provided makes the child act inappropriately. "I had told him that he was not allowed to fight and yet he hit his kindergarten classmate". These types of parents do not understand that it is not enough to explain to the child what they are allowed to do as long as they are unintentionally conveying the exact opposite; "although he tells the child not to fight with his colleagues, he witnesses daily such scenes in the family in which the father abuses his wife" (Bocsa, 2012).

In the education of the child who is in the period of primary socialisation, it is advisable to adopt an appropriate educational style. Thus, the American psychologist Diana Baumrind highlighted the relationship between the educational attitudes of the parents and the school results of the child as follows:

1. The guiding style - the parents clearly explain their requirements, control the children's activity and expect good results from them. They guide the children's activity, are emotionally close to them and encourage them to express their opinions
2. The authoritative style - they are more distant and ask the child to obey rigid requirements without explaining the purpose "you have to do this because I want you to"
3. The permissive style - permissive parents who express warmth and affection, who rarely punish the children and do not impose many restrictions on them. (Bocsa, 2012)

The relationship between these educational styles and the consequences on a psycho-social level have been found since kindergarten or the early school period (table no. 1)

Table 1

	Guiding style	Authoritative style	Permissive style
Kindergarten	- independent	- moody	- immature
School	- friendly	- insecure	- passive
	- energetic	- withdrawn	- dependant
	- self-confident		

Source: author's own development

The relationship between the socialisation process and deviant behaviours

Sociologists define deviance as the set of behaviours and states that members of a group judge as inconsistent with their expectations, norms or values and that produce sanctions on their part

(Boudon & Cusson 1997). However, deviance as a phenomenon should not be confused with teenage rebellion. Deviance has a relative character in relation to a normative context, what is condemned in one culture or era is often tolerated in another culture. For example "killing someone is a serious crime, but not for the soldier at war who is paid to kill".

However, there are tendencies towards deviant behaviour since childhood and adolescence. The problem arises when trying to find an explanation for deviant behaviour from childhood that continues into adolescence and adulthood. The phenomenon of juvenile delinquency is gaining momentum these days. Some psychologists believe that juvenile delinquency is due to the weakening of the adolescent's bond with society. This connection is made up of 4 components: attachment to a person who motivates the individual (usually from the family), enrolment of the teenager in an academic or professional project, involvement in activities that leave him little free time, conviction that the laws must be respected. Young people who are not in good relations with their parents because the latter are poor educators, being passive, inconstant in their attitude, not establishing a clear discipline and not being interested in the children's development push the latter towards deviant behaviour. The school situation of the youth who have deviant behaviour shows a series of characteristics that show poor integration or even disgust with school with low academic results. Thus an apparently meaningless act such as vandalism can be understood as an exciting and amusing playful activity (Coord. Raymond Boudon & Cusson 1997).

Teenagers can be capable of a series of antisocial behaviours based, as we mentioned above, on educational deficiencies stemming from primary socialisation, on the existence of problematic situations in the family that lead to the adoption of behaviour according to the pattern formed in the family. There are two types of behavioural disorders found in adolescents: oppositional defiant disorder and conduct disorder.

Oppositional disorder manifests itself through defiance of parents or authorities, aggression, inability to self-control and disobedience to norms. This opposition appears from an early age. This oppositional defiant disorder is often seen in young children who cry or scream when they are denied a wish. Teenagers manifest themselves by defying and offending his parents, then they may become aggressive, hitting, destroying objects, etc. In its severe forms, oppositional defiant disorder in adolescence can lead to truancy, integration into ill-famed gangs, or even running away from home. This antisocial behaviour is associated with social, family and genetic factors.

Conduct disorder is manifested by frequent violation of moral and social norms, violation of the rights of others, consumption of drugs and alcohol, theft, lying, aggression, vagrancy, prostitution. The main factor of this deviant behaviour is the family environment characterized by disintegration, aggression, disorganization, etc. Statistically, it was found that 90% of the teenagers who received physical corrections from their parents in their childhood also applied physical corrections to other people. Accentuated personalities or even some minor mental disorders can worsen if the family environment is not appropriate leading to deviance. The success or failure of socialisation in the family group is conditioned by a number of factors. Balanced affective climate characterized by a level of satisfaction. Emotional imbalances, tension, violence, conflicts are incriminating when we talk about behavioural disorders. Symmetrical and complementary relationships of parents are related to socio-cultural requirements (www.socializarea.wordpress.com)

Conclusions

In essence, we may state that although all three links of socialisation (primary, secondary and continuous) are important, we must pay special attention to primary socialisation. We have to be careful about what we want to transmit to the child as socio-cultural values on the one hand, and on the other hand what we transmit to the child involuntarily (unintentional socialisation). In this sense, social workers must know these stages, especially when they offer advice and support to young families who plan to have a child. Future parents must know that they will serve as a cultural model for the child and that to a large extent they will be responsible for the success or failure of primary socialisation and implicitly the risk of the child's deviant behaviour.

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